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Physicochemical, microbial and sensory qualities of Zobo (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.) drink blended with lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus* Stapf)

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ABSTRACT

Zobo (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) is a widely consumed traditional dark-red beverage in Nigeria and West Africa. This study aimed to enhance its shelf life by incorporating lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*), a tropical herb known for its antimicrobial and medicinal properties. Five formulations were prepared: 100% Zobo (control), and blends containing 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% lemongrass. Samples were subjected to physicochemical, microbial, and sensory analyses using standard methods. The results revealed that pH values increased progressively with higher lemongrass concentrations, ranging from 2.5 in the control to 9.5 in the highest blend. Brix values remained constant across all samples, while total soluble solids (TSS) increased, with sample E (20% lemongrass) recording the highest value (300 mg/L). Specific gravity varied slightly, with sample B showing the highest value (98.66 g/mol). By day 21 of storage, the control sample exhibited the highest microbial loads, including total plate count (11.5×10^4 cfu/mL), coliforms, *Salmonella*, and *Staphylococcus*. In contrast, samples with lemongrass (especially B to E) demonstrated improved microbial stability, with no detectable coliforms and reduced bacterial counts. However, sample E recorded the highest total fungal count (282.0×10^4 cfu/mL). A total of four microbial isolates were identified: *Staphylococcus* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., and *Micrococcus* spp. The findings suggest that lemongrass incorporation improves the physicochemical quality and microbial shelf stability of Zobo drink, with moderate concentrations offering the most balanced preservation effect.

Keywords: Microbial, Sensory Qualities, Zobo, Lemon Grass

1. INTRODUCTION

Zobo (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) is a dark-red hibiscus-based beverage known as a popular traditional drink in Nigeria and other West African countries (Olawale *et al.*, 2023). Zobo beverage is well known for its energising flavour, vibrant and health benefits, which include antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Jaffee *et al.*, 2018). Zobo drink is extracted from the dried Reddish Purple calyces of the plant *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, the calyces are used to produce herbal tea and other products (Mariod *et al.*, 2021).

Zobo drink is traditionally prepared by steeping dried calyx of *Hibiscus* in water, often sweetened with sugar and spiced with ginger, cloves, and other flavourings such as orange, pineapple, cucumber and apple to enhance the taste (Kehinde and Augustine, 2022). Additionally, it is boiled in water for 10 to 15 minutes to extract the pigment (Mariod *et al.*, 2021).

Zobo drink may harbour both foodborne microorganisms, which are responsible for spoilage and poisoning (Mariod *et al.*, 2021). The processes of zobo production and packaging may increase the chances of microbial contamination (Mariod *et al.*, 2021). Chemical contaminants and microorganisms such as *Streptococcus*, *Micrococcus* and *Enterobacter* have been reported in commercial edibles/drinks (Ajani *et al.*, 2025).

Furthermore, the most frequently reported fungal genera are *Aspergillus*, *Rhizopus* and *Candida* (Bristone *et al.*, 2018).

Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) is one of the most commonly grown crops in tropical climates, commonly used as a cooking herb or as an alternative herbal remedy in treating or preventing of some diseases (Umoren *et al.*, 2022). Lemongrass is well known for its anti-oxidants, anti-microbial, anti-hypertensive, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anxiolytic properties (Putri *et al.*, 2023). They are considered quintessential food and feed additives at the industrial level (Putri *et al.*, 2023).

Lemongrass contains many useful chemical compounds such as flavonoids, polyphenols, alkaloids and essential oils with antibacterial properties and antioxidant potential (Putra *et al.*, 2023). Presently, Zobo production is not standardised and thus hinders its large-scale production due to uncontrollable microorganism spoilage and preservative problems, which makes its fermentation take approximately 24 hours after production.

Therefore, finding an alternative to improve the shelf life is essential. The study aims to increase the shelf life of the drink utilising lemon grass.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out in the laboratory of Food Science and Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria.

2. 2. Source of and collection of materials

Dried zobo calyx, Ginger, Cloves, Garlic, flavouring, Pineapple, etc., were all obtained from Oja Odan International Market, Oja Odan, Yewa North, Ogun State, Nigeria. The lemon grass was collected from the botanical garden at the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria.

2. 3. Preparation of Zobo drink

The preparation of Zobo drink was carried out using the method described by Mohammed *et al.* (2022) with a slight modification. The ingredients used in the preparation of Zobo drink include 30g of dried Zobo calyx, 20g of ginger, 1 teaspoon of cloves, 20g of garlic, half (½) teaspoon of flavouring, 200 g of lemon grass and 2000 mL of tap water.

The dried Zobo calyx was sorted to remove dirt and then washed three times with tap water. The cloves and ginger were washed thoroughly with tap water and peeled using a stainless-steel knife. The Zobo calyx and the other ingredients were transferred into a large stainless pot and then subjected to boiling for 40 minutes. Furthermore, the lemon grass was thoroughly washed and then transferred into the pot for juice extraction.

2. 4. Formulation of Zobo Blends

Five blends of Zobo drink were prepared and were labelled blend A, B, C, D and E. Blend A was original Zobo drink (Control), blend B was Zobo drink using 5% lemongrass, blend C was Zobo drink using 10% lemongrass, blend D was Zobo drink using 15% lemongrass, blend E was Zobo drink using 20% lemongrass (Table 1).

Table 1. Formulation of Zobo Blends.

Sample Code	Drink Formulations
Sample A	Zobo (Control): 100 %
Sample B	95% Zobo + 5% Lemon grass
Sample C	90% Zobo + 10% Lemon grass
Sample D	85% Zobo + 15% Lemon grass
Sample E	80% Zobo + 20% Lemon grass

2. 5. Physicochemical Analysis

The physicochemical analysis was carried out according to Oumer *et al.* (2022). The pH was determined using the electrometric method, the BRIX was determined using the refractometric method, Total suspended solids (TSS) using the gravimetric method, while the Specific Gravity was determined using the standard method

2. 6. Microbial Analysis

2. 6. 1. Media preparation and Serial dilution

All glassware was oven dried for 10 hours, then allowed to cool before use. All the media were prepared according to the manufacturer's description. Then, they were sterilized using an autoclave at 121 °C for 15 minutes and allowed to cool at 45 °C. Each blend of the zobo drink was serially diluted. Exactly, 1 ml of each sample was measured into 9 ml of distilled water in

a sterile test tube, shaken, then another 1 ml from the dilution was transferred into another sterile test tube labelled 10^{-2} . These procedures were repeated to a dilution of 10^{-4} dilutions, stopped with a non-absorbent cotton wool and aluminium foil.

2. 6. 2. Determination of Total Plate Count (TPC)

Exactly, 1 ml from the 10^{-4} dilution was aseptically transferred into a sterile petri dish for each plating. About 10 ml of the cooled molten Nutrient agar was poured into the petri dish and gently shaken for distribution of the inoculum throughout the medium, allowed to solidify,

2. 6. 3. Total Coliform, Staphylococcus and Salmonella Count

Exact procedure for the total plate count was repeated for the total coliform, staphylococcus, and salmonella count using MacConkey agar, Baird-Parker agar and bismuth sulphite agar media, respectively, then incubated at 35 °C for 48 hours (Adebayo *et al.*, 2018).

2. 6. 4. Identification of Isolates

The bacteria isolates were identified macroscopically, microscopically (gram staining) and through various biochemical tests (Catalase, Oxidase, Urease, Oxidase and Sugar fermentation test) The morphological characterization of fungi isolates was based on the macroscopic examination: colour, texture and pigment and microscopic examination were also carried out by using lactophenol cotton blue stain (Cheesebrough, 2006; Oluoyeneye *et al.*, 2025).

2. 6. 5. Determination of Fungal Colony Count

Exact procedure for the above media was repeated for Fungi Colony Count (FCC), the Potato dextrose Agar (PDA) was incubated at 28 °C for 48hours (Adebayo *et al.*, 2018).

2. 7. Sensory Evaluation

A sensory panel consisting of 20 panellists and students from the Department of Food Science and Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria. The sensory evaluation was performed on the samples by checking for appearance, aroma, taste, texture and general suitability. The participants evaluated the sample using a 9-point hedonic scale quality analysis, classified as 9 = Extremely desirable, 8 = Very much desirable, 7 = Moderately desirable, 6 = Slightly undesirable, 5 = Neither desirable nor undesirable, 4 = Slightly undesirable, 3 = Moderately undesirable, 2 = Very much undesirable, 1 = Extremely undesirable.

2. 8. Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. The result was presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Physicochemical Properties of Zobo Drink Blended with Lemon Grass

The physicochemical analysis of Zobo drink blended with lemon grass is reported in Table 2. The pH of zobo drinks ranged from 2.5 to 9.5 and increased as the concentration of lemongrass increased. Sample A has the lowest pH (2.5) while Sample E has the highest pH (9.5). The Brix value was constant across all zobo drink blends, indicating that there was no drop in sugar content. Furthermore, the highest TSS was recorded in sample E (300 mg/L) while the lowest was in the control (100 mg/L). Generally, the control sample had lower TSS than the mixed sample. The specific gravity varied from 98.33 to 98.66 g/mol. Sample B has the highest value (98.66 g/mol), while samples A and E have an equally low value (98.33 g/mol).

Table 2. Physico-chemical analysis of Zobo drink blended with lemon grass.

SAMPLE	pH	BRIX (%)	TSS (mg/L)	SPECIFIC GRAVITY (g/mol)
Sample A	2.5	1	100	98.33
Sample B	3.8	1	200	98.66
Sample C	4.6	1	200	98.55
Sample D	5.5	1	200	98.52
Sample E	9.5	1	300	98.33

Sample A = Zobo (control), Sample B = 95% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample C = 90% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample D = 85% Zobo + 15% lemon grass, Sample E = 80% Zobo + 20% lemon grass

3. 2. Microbial Analysis of Zobo Drink blended with Lemon Grass

The total viable microbial count for the Zobo Drink blended with Lemon grass at days 7, 14 and 21 is presented in Tables 3, 4 and 5. At day 7, the highest total plate count (TPC) was recorded in sample D (6.0×10^4 cfu /mL) while the lowest was in sample C (1.0×10^4 cfu /mL). The highest total salmonella count (TSC) was recorded in sample D (4.5×10^4 cfu /mL) while the lowest was equal in samples A and E (0.5×10^2 cfu /mL). The highest total fungi count (TFC) was recorded in sample E (2.5×10^4 cfu /mL) while the lowest was in sample D (0.5×10^4 cfu /mL). The highest staphylococcus count (TSAC) was only recorded in sample A (0.5×10^4 cfu /mL) with no growth in samples B to E. Furthermore, total coliform count (TCC) was not recorded across the blends.

At day 14, the highest total plate count (TPC) was recorded in sample A (10.5×10^4 cfu /mL) while the lowest was in sample B (3.5×10^4 cfu /mL). The highest staphylococcus count (TSAC) was recorded in sample A (5.0×10^4 cfu /mL) while no growth was recorded in sample C. The highest Salmonella count (TSC) was recorded in sample A (20.0×10^4 cfu /mL), with the lowest being in Sample B (3.5×10^4 cfu /mL).

The highest total fungi count (TFC) was recorded in sample D (91.5×10^4 cfu /mL) while the lowest was in sample D (24.0×10^4 cfu /mL). Furthermore, total coliform count (TCC) was not recorded across the blends.

At day 21, the highest total plate count (TPC) was recorded in sample A (11.5×10^4 cfu /mL) while the lowest was equally in samples D and E (2.0×10^4 cfu /mL). The highest total coliform count (CC) was recorded in sample A (1.0×10^4 cfu /mL) while no growth was recorded in sample B-E. The highest staphylococcus count (TSAC) was recorded in sample A (6.5×10^4 cfu /mL), while the lowest was in samples B and D (2.5×10^4 cfu /mL). The highest Salmonella count (TSC) was recorded in sample A (34.5×10^4 cfu /mL), with the lowest being in Sample B (5.5×10^4 cfu /mL). The highest total fungi count (TFC) was recorded in sample E (282.0×10^4 cfu /mL) while the lowest was in sample B (134×10^4 cfu /mL). Furthermore, a totals of four isolates, namely *Staphylococcus* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., and *Micrococcus* spp., was recorded in the study (Table 6).

Table 3. Microbial Load ($\times 10^4$ cfu/ml) in Zobo drink blended with lemon grass extract at Day 7.

SAMPLE	TPC	TCC	TSAC	TSC	TFC
Sample A	3.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	0.5±0.7	0.5±0.7	1.0±1.4
Sample B	4.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	1.0±1.4	2.0±2.8
Sample C	1.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	3.5±0.7	1.5±0.7
Sample D	6.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	4.5±0.7	0.5±0.7
Sample E	2.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.5±0.7	2.5±2.1

TPC (Total plate count), TCC (Total coliform count), TSAC (Total salmonella count), TSC (Total staphylococcus count), TFC (Total fungi count).

Sample A = Zobo (control), Sample B = 95% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample C = 90% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample D = 85% Zobo + 15% lemon grass, Sample E = 80% Zobo + 20% lemon grass

Table 4. Microbial Load ($\times 10^4$ cfu/ml) in Zobo drink blended with lemon grass extract at Day 14.

SAMPLE	TPC	TCC	TSAC	TSC	TFC
Sample A	10.5±9.1	0.0±0.0	5.0±0.0	20.0±1.4	72.0±1.4
Sample B	3.5±0.7	0.0±0.0	2.0±0.0	3.5±0.7	76.0±1.4
Sample C	10.0±7.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	11.0±4.2	40.0±1.4
Sample D	9.5±7.7	0.0±0.0	1.5±0.7	6.5±7.7	91.5±0.7
Sample E	9.0±8.4	0.0±0.0	1.5±0.7	8.0±4.2	24.0±1.4

TPC (Total plate count), TCC (Total coliform count), TSAC (Total salmonella count), TSC (Total staphylococcus count), TFC (Total fungi count).

Sample A = Zobo (control), Sample B = 95% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample C = 90% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample D = 85% Zobo + 15% lemon grass, Sample E = 80% Zobo + 20% lemon grass.

Table 5. Microbial Load ($\times 10^4$ cfu/ml) in Zobo drink blended with lemon grass extract at Day 21.

SAMPLE	TPC	TCC	TSAC	TSC	TFC
Sample A	11.5±3.5	1.0±0.0	6.5±0.7	34.5±2.1	145.0±2.8
Sample B	5.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	2.5±0.7	5.5±0.7	134.0±3.5
Sample C	5.5±2.1	0.0±0.0	3.0±1.4	9.5±2.1	238.5±3.5
Sample D	2.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	2.5±0.7	25.5±2.1	243.0±1.4
Sample E	2.0±1.4	0.0±0.0	4.0±0.0	28.5±0.7	282.0±1.4

TPC (Total plate count), TCC (Total coliform count), TSAC (Total salmonella count), TSC (Total staphylococcus count), TFC (Total fungi count)

Sample A = Zobo (control), Sample B= 95% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample C = 90% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample D = 85% Zobo+15% lemon grass, Sample E = 80% Zobo + 20% lemon grass

Table 6. Biochemical Test for Bacterial Isolate.

Sample	Color	Shape	Gram's stain	Gram's reaction	Catalase test	Urease test	Oxidase test	Sugar fermentation			Suspected organism
								G	F	L	
A	Cream	Round Flat	Cocci	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.
	Cream	Glossy Flat	Rod	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Bacilli</i> spp.
B	Cream	Entire flat	Rod	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.
	Cream	Soft smooth	Cocci	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.
C	Cream	Round Flat	Cocci	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp
	Cream	Entire flat	Rod	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.

D	Cream	Round flat	Cocci	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.
	Yellow	Entire flat	Cocci	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Micrococcus</i> spp.
E	Yellow	Entire flat	Cocci	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Micrococcus</i> spp.
	Cream	Round	Cocci	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.

Key: +ve (positive reaction), -ve (negative reaction), G = glucose, F = fructose, L = Lactose.

3. 3. Sensory Evaluation of Zobo Drink blended with Lemon Grass

The appearance of the Zobo drinks ranged from 8.15 to 8.50, the highest value was recorded in sample A (8.50) while the lowest was equally in samples D and E (8.15). The colour of the Zobo drink ranged from 7.95 to 8.40. Samples B and C had the lowest mean values (7.95), while the highest was recorded in sample A (8.40).

The Zobo drink's taste ranged between 7.70 and 8.40. The highest value was recorded in sample A (8.40) while the lowest was in sample E (7.70). The mean aroma of the zobo drink ranges from 7.90 ± 8.10. Sample B (7.90) had the lowest value, while sample E (8.10) had the highest. The Zobo drink's flavour ranged from 7.70 to 8.15. Sample E (7.70) had the lowest value while sample A (8.15) had the highest.

The willingness to buy ranged from 7.90 to 8.40. Sample D had the lowest mean value (7.90) while Sample A had the highest (8.40). Based on the overall acceptability of all the samples, sample A had the highest mean value (8.50), followed by sample B (8.30) and sample C (8.25), while samples D and E (8.05) had the same mean value (Table 7).

Table 7. Sensory evaluation of Zobo drink treated with lemongrass extract.

Samples	Appearance	Color	Taste	Aroma	Flavor	Willingness to buy	Overall availability
Sample A	8.50±0.60	8.40±0.60	8.40±0.68	8.00±0.86	8.15±0.49	8.40±0.82	8.50±0.69
Sample B	8.00±0.32	7.95±0.76	8.05±0.69	7.90±0.97	7.90±0.78	8.30±0.66	8.30±0.66
Sample C	8.20±0.53	7.95±0.76	8.05±0.60	7.85±0.81	7.95±0.76	8.30±0.73	8.25±0.64
Sample D	8.15±0.58	8.15±0.75	8.15±0.81	7.95±0.82	7.80±0.83	7.90±0.78	8.05±0.83
Sample E	8.15±0.58	8.00±0.79	7.70±0.45	8.10±0.32	7.70±0.12	7.95±0.24	8.05±0.54

Sample A = Zobo (control), Sample B = 95% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample C = 90% Zobo + 10% lemon grass, Sample D = 85% Zobo + 15% lemon grass, Sample E = 80% Zobo + 20% lemon grass

4. DISCUSSION

The physicochemical properties of Zobo drink blended with varying concentrations of lemongrass showed significant variation across samples, particularly in pH, total soluble solids (TSS), and specific gravity. The observed pH values range showed a clear trend of increasing pH with rising lemongrass concentration. This suggests that lemongrass possesses alkalizing properties, which progressively neutralise the inherent acidity of Zobo (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) drink. The low pH value in sample A corresponds with a more acidic formulation, while the high pH value in sample E indicates a shift toward alkalinity due to higher lemongrass content. This finding is consistent with previous studies indicating that lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) contains basic phytochemicals, such as citral and flavonoids, which may contribute to increased pH in food systems (Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2018; Bepete and Eze, 2020).

The Brix values, which indicate sugar concentration, remained constant across all samples. This stability suggests that the addition of lemongrass did not affect the sugar content of the Zobo drink, implying no dilution or degradation of natural sugars during the blending process. However, variations in total soluble solids (TSS) were observed, with sample E (highest lemongrass concentration) while the control sample (Zobo without lemongrass) had the lowest. This increase in TSS could be attributed to the release of additional phytochemicals, organic acids, and minerals from lemongrass, enriching the overall solute content of the drink (Adenuga and Olatunbosun, 2017; Akinmoladun *et al.*, 2020).

The specific gravity of the samples ranged narrowly, with sample B exhibiting the highest value. Specific gravity, a measure of solution density, may vary due to the molecular weight of dissolved substances. Although the variation is minor, it suggests some structural differences among samples in terms of their dissolved solid content and composition. The comparable low values observed in samples A and E indicate that either very little or a very high amount of lemongrass contributes similarly to the beverage's density, possibly due to saturation or solubility limits (Afolabi and Odetokun, 2019).

The microbiological evaluation of Zobo drinks blended with lemongrass over a 21-day storage period revealed dynamic microbial changes influenced by both storage time and lemongrass concentration. At day 7, low microbial loads were generally observed, reflecting initial product stability. However, sample D recorded the highest Total Plate Count (TPC) and Total Salmonella Count (TSC), which may indicate limited antimicrobial effects of lemongrass in that formulation. In contrast, sample C recorded the lowest TPC, suggesting stronger antibacterial activity, possibly due to a more effective lemongrass concentration or synergistic inhibition with Zobo phytochemicals (Obboh *et al.*, 2018).

The Total Fungal Count (TFC) peaked in sample E while sample D had the lowest pointing to variability in antifungal protection across blends. Only sample A showed measurable Staphylococcus count (TSAC), and importantly, Total Coliform Count (TCC) was absent across all samples at this stage, suggesting acceptable hygiene and safe initial microbial quality (Omemu and Bankole, 2015).

By day 14, microbial proliferation intensified. Sample A demonstrated the highest microbial burden across multiple indicators, TPC, TSC, and TSAC indicating accelerated spoilage and weak preservation. This could be attributed to low antimicrobial efficacy or degradation of inhibitory compounds over time. Sample D exhibited the highest TFC, underscoring the susceptibility of this sample to fungal contamination during extended storage. Sample B, on the other hand, consistently recorded the lowest microbial levels, suggesting an

optimal lemongrass concentration conferring enhanced antimicrobial protection (Akinmoladun *et al.*, 2020).

At day 21, spoilage indicators became more pronounced, especially in sample A, which had the highest TPC, TSC, TSAC and the only recorded TCC. This highlights a breakdown in microbial control and increased food safety risk. In contrast, samples D and E had the lowest TPC, showing improved stability. The exponential rise in fungal load in sample E signals the need for antifungal formulation optimisation in that blend.

The detection of *Staphylococcus* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., and *Micrococcus* spp., throughout the study is typical for traditional beverages to reflect both beneficial fermenters and spoilage organisms (Adegoke *et al.*, 2020). Notably, the presence of *Lactobacillus* spp. may indicate a degree of probiotic potential, while *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* spp. may pose food safety concerns at high levels (Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2018; Obadina *et al.*, 2018).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study shows that combining Zobo drink with lemongrass significantly affects its physicochemical properties, particularly pH and total soluble solids (TSS). Higher lemongrass concentrations raise the pH, potentially improving taste and reducing gastrointestinal discomfort. The increase in TSS suggests a nutritional boost, while stable Brix values indicate consistent sweetness. Minor variations in specific gravity confirm the impact of lemongrass on the drink.

The lemongrass enhances Zobo drink quality and acceptability, with future research needed on sensory attributes and microbial stability. Over 21 days, microbial loads rose in all samples; however, sample A (with no lemongrass) showed the highest spoilage risk by day 21, while sample B effectively suppressed microbes. Most samples had no coliforms and contained beneficial *Lactobacillus* spp., highlighting safety and functional benefits. Nonetheless, increased fungal growth in some samples, especially sample E, suggests antifungal strategies are necessary. Overall, lemongrass shows promise as a natural preservative in Zobo beverages. Further research is recommended to explore its antifungal optimization, its synergistic effect with other plant-based preservatives, and to validate its sensory, nutritional, and probiotic benefits in functional beverage development.

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